

A Study of Convergence Properties of Adaptive Algorithms For Robotic Systems

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Abstract: A comparison is made between two types of adaptive control algorithms. The first type is based on Lyapunov functions and mechanical energy considerations play a key roll in their construction. A second method studied here involves a majorizing function approach in which a linear function bounds the modeling error which implicitly involves different types of nonlinearities. A gravity vector nonlinearity is studied as an example. This latter method is more of a dominant eigenvalue method and is compared to the time constant approach using the Lyapunov functions.

I. Introduction:

In building an adaptive controller for any system under consideration it is essential to establish that the algorithm developed converges to a stable solution. Adaptive control methods have great applicability for the problem of finding parameters of a controller so that the tracking error converges. A number of interesting reviews of the various methods [1,3] have both compared the different approaches as well as attempted to unify the overall theory. Adaptive Control Theory has been applied in the early work involving the "MIT Rule" [4] and some other development work in the 1960's [5,6].

There are two general types of adaptive control algorithms:

- (1) **Direct** - (model reference, deterministic) in which the goal is to compare the behavior of the controlled plant with a reference model so that by changing controller parameters, the plant's output follows the output of a reference model.
- (2) **Indirect** (self tuning, stochastic, parameters need to be identified). This method requires identification of parameters of the plant and then adjustment of the controller to account for the new parameter estimates. Here it is assumed that the parameters change slowly within the sampling rate (cf. Koivo and Guo [7]). Other researchers, however, feel the problem of the quickly changing dynamics is considered too severe for this assumption to hold [8,9].

There are two necessary requirements with developing an adaptive control algorithm:

- (1) Prove convergence of $e(t)$ and $\dot{e}(t)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$.
- (2) Prove convergence of the parameter update law.

One must be very careful not to allow the V function to "get stuck" in the sense that \dot{e} goes to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$ but e does not. Slotine [11] goes to great effort to always prove this point. Initially, this was a criticism of the original MIT rule [4].

In summary there are many good methods in the literature to design adaptive controllers using V functions as indicated in [1]. These procedures can be expanded into other areas of robotic research which include methods to exploit system dynamics (e.g. Khosla and Kanade [12]), and methods involving dynamic compensation with models that differ slightly from the true system model (Leahy [13]).

II. Formulation Of The Adaptive Control Problem:

To formulate an adaptive control problem, use is made of a Lagrangian formulation for a robot manipulator [14]. For an n-link robot arm, the Lagrange equations of motion can be written:

$$t_i = \sum_{j=1}^n D_{ij}(q) \ddot{q}_j + \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n C_{ijk}(q) \dot{q}_j \dot{q}_k + G_i(q) \quad (1)$$

- where:
- t_i = force or torque on joint i
 - q_i = joint angle or translation of prismatic joint i
 - \dot{q}_i, \ddot{q}_i = velocity, acceleration of q_i
 - D_{ij} = effective and/or coupling inertia of joint i
 - C_{ij} = Centrifugal and Coriolis forces at joint i
 - G_i = gravity load

Equation (1) can be written for simplicity as:

$$D(q) \ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q}) + G(q) = t \quad (2)$$

by letting $C(q, \dot{q}) = C^j(q, \dot{q}) \dot{q} \quad (3)$

$$G(q) = G^j(q) q \quad (4)$$

equation (2) is now of the form:

$$D(q) \ddot{q} + C^j(q, \dot{q}) \dot{q} + G^j(q) q = t \quad (5)$$

A state vector is now defined as:

$$x = \text{col} [q, \dot{q}] \quad (6)$$

then: $\dot{x} = A_p(x, t) x + B_p(x, t) t \quad (7)$

for the appropriate A_p, B_p matrices which are nonlinear functions of the state variables. If the actuator dynamics are now included, the torque can be broken up into a component due to link structure motion and a second component due to nonlinear motor and friction torques. The state model for the robot actuator can then be written:

$$\dot{x}_p = A(x_p, t) x_p + B(x_p, t) u \quad (8)$$

To formulate the adaptive control problem, a model-reference adaptive control (MRAC) method will first be applied. Define a reference model:

$$\text{Reference Model: } \dot{y} = A_m y + B_m r \quad (9)$$

where y is an $n \times 1$ reference state vector, $r = n \times 1$ reference input vector, and:

$$A_m = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I \\ -L1 & -L2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B_m = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ L1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where $L1 = n \times n$ diagonal matrix with terms w_j and

$L2 = n \times n$ diagonal matrix with terms $2; w_i$

Thus n uncoupled second order ordinary differential equations result of the form:

$$\ddot{y}_i + 2 \zeta_i w_i \dot{y}_i + w_i^2 y_i = w_i r \quad (11)$$

where r = the reference input (ideal robotic trajectory). Define the reference model error:

$$e(t) = y(t) - xp(t) \quad (12)$$

For a MRAC design problem, it can be formulated as follows: Find K_p, K_u such that:

$$u(t) = K_p xp + K_u r \quad (13)$$

produces the stable control law:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e(t) = 0 \quad (14)$$

III - The Lyapunov Stability Method:

The second method of Lyapunov applies to the autonomous system:

$$\dot{x} = f(x), \quad f(0) = 0 \quad (15)$$

where x is an n vector. A scalar Lyapunov function $V(x)$ is selected and its total time derivative can be written:

$$W = dV/dt = \partial V / \partial x_1 \dot{x}_1 + \partial V / \partial x_2 \dot{x}_2 + \dots + \partial V / \partial x_n \dot{x}_n \quad (16)$$

which can be written in dot product notation:

$$W = \langle \text{grad } V, f \rangle \quad (17)$$

We will utilize one simplified version of Lyapunov's asymptotic stability theorem as follows:

Theorem 1: Given the differential system of equation (15), the equilibrium is asymptotically stable if it is possible to find a positive definite $V(x)$ such that $V(0)=0$ and W is negative definite. The first example considered here [10] illustrates the relationship between the classical position gain K_d and the velocity feedback gain K_v using mechanical energy considerations.

Example 1: For a robotic system, a torque control law is chosen of the form:

$$\tau = -K_p e - K_v \dot{e} \quad (18)$$

The manipulator dynamics are given by:

$$D \ddot{q} + C \dot{q} = \tau \quad (19)$$

The Lyapunov function is chosen to be:

$$V = 1/2 [e^T K_p e + \dot{q}^T D \dot{q}] \quad (20)$$

where in this case e is the tracking error ($e=q-q_d$) and q_d is the desired trajectory. It can be shown that $(D-2C)$ is antisymmetric. Note V depends on the

manipulator kinetic energy $(1/2 \dot{q}^T D \dot{q})$ and another

term $1/2 e^T K_p e$ which depends on the d.c. gain matrix. With some calculation it is easy to show that:

$$\dot{V} = -\dot{q}^T K_d \dot{q} \leq 0 \quad (21)$$

if $(D-2C)$ is antisymmetric.

Note the V function depends on K_p , but \dot{V} depends on K_d . To show the system cannot get stuck with $e \neq 0$ and $\dot{V} = 0$, we see if $\dot{q} = 0$,

$$\ddot{q} = D^{-1} (\tau - C\dot{q}) = -D^{-1} K_p e \neq 0 \quad (22)$$

Thus q would not remain in equilibrium if $q \neq q_d$, the desired trajectory. A second example describes a nonlinear spring [10].

Example 2 - Consider a nonlinear spring damper system:

$$\ddot{x} + b(\dot{x}) + K(x) = 0 \quad (23)$$

with $b(\dot{x}) > 0$ for $\dot{x} \neq 0$ (24)

$$x K(x) > 0 \text{ for } x \neq 0 \quad (25)$$

A Lyapunov function is chosen to be the sum of both the kinetic and potential energy of the system:

$$\text{i.e. } V = 1/2 \dot{x}^2 + \int_0^x K(y) dy \quad (26)$$

Then by calculation:

$$\dot{V} = -\dot{x} b(\dot{x}) \leq 0 \text{ from the hypothesis.} \quad (27)$$

To show that $x \neq 0$, and $\dot{V} = 0$ can never occur, we have $\dot{x} b(\dot{x}) = 0$ only if $\dot{x} = 0$. If $\dot{x} = 0$, implies:

$$\ddot{x} = -K(x) \neq 0 \text{ if } x \neq 0 \quad (28)$$

from the hypothesis.

A third example illustrates how energy dissipates along the equations of motion. **Example 3:**

For a strictly linear system:

$$m \ddot{y} + K_d \dot{y} + K_s y = 0 \quad (29)$$

if $m=K_d=K_s=1$, and the state variables are chosen as:

$$x = \text{col}[x_1, x_2] = \text{col}[y, \dot{y}] \quad (30)$$

Then:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

if $x(0) = \text{col}[1,0]$ this can be shown to satisfy:

$$x_1(t) = 2/\sqrt{3} e^{-t/2} \sin(\sqrt{3}/2 t + \pi/3) \quad (32a)$$

$$x_2(t) = -2/\sqrt{3} e^{-t/2} \sin(\sqrt{3}/2 t) \quad (32b)$$

To derive the Lyapunov function, note the kinetic energy in the moving mass is:

$$\text{K.E.} = 1/2 m \dot{x}_1^2 = 1/2 m x_2^2 \quad (33)$$

The spring has a potential energy $1/2 K_s(x_1)x_1$.

The total stored energy is:

$$V = 1/2 K_s x_1^2 + 1/2 m x_2^2 \quad (34)$$

with some calculation:

$$\dot{V} = -K_d x_1 x_2 = -K_d x_2^2 \quad (35)$$

or using the values specified before for m, K_d, K_s , it is seen that:

$$V = 1/2 x_1^2 + 1/2 x_2^2 \quad (36a)$$

$$\dot{V} = -x_2^2 \quad (36b)$$

Thus the loci for constant energy are circles in the x_1 - x_2 phase plane. \dot{V} is always negative, thus the circles shrink with time and the total stored energy decreases with increasing time. Figure (1) illustrates the V curves parametrically with time. Figure (2) illustrates $\dot{V}, V(t)$. For this example it can be shown:

$$V = 2/3 e^{-t} [\sin^2(\sqrt{3}/2 t) + \sin^2(\sqrt{3}/2 t + \pi/3)] \quad (37a)$$

$$\dot{V} = -4/3 e^{-t} \sin^2[\sqrt{3}/2 t] \quad (37b)$$

IV - Transient Response Using Lyapunov Functions:

In order to compare the Lyapunov method versus a majorizing function method, it is necessary to develop a method of characterizing the transient response using the selected Lyapunov function. The equilibrium of the autonomous system (which would be closed loop) must be stable. Example four will consider a dominant time constant approach to estimate the speed of response of convergence.

Example 4:

A system is characterized by:

$$\ddot{x}_1 = -x_1 / T \quad (38)$$

we select: $V(x_1) = [x_1]^2 / 2$ (39)

Then: $W = dV/dt = \partial V / \partial x_1 \dot{x}_1 = x_1 [-x_1/T] = -x_1^2 / T$ (40)

Note: $V(x_1)$ is positive definite, W is negative definite if $T > 0$. To examine speed of response, it is necessary to normalize the rate at which the Lyapunov function changes. Here it is seen that:

$$-dV/dt / V = -W / V = 2/T \quad (41)$$

implies $V = V(0) e^{-[2/T] t}$ (42)

Thus V varies with time along the motion. Since the Lyapunov function depends on the system's energy, it depends on the squares of the state variables.

Hence the time constant for the variation of the L function is twice the time constant of the system (i.e. $x_1 = -x_1/T$). Thus once a V function is found then the ratio W/V simply defines twice the system's time constant. This now provides a basis for comparison to a majorizing function approach.

V. A Majorizing Function Approach

In this approach the objective is to have the state vector $x(t)$ follow a trajectory $x_d(t)$. The tracking error:

$$e(t) = \theta_d(t) - \theta(t) \quad (43)$$

is the variable we wish to bound via a linear function of exponential order. With reference to figure (3), the equations of motion describing the error $e(t)$ would integrate forward in time (assuming t applied $=m_1 \theta_d$ but t required $=m_1 \theta + m_1 g l \cos \theta$).

Thus:

$$m_1 \ddot{e}(t) = m_1 g l \cos \theta(t) \quad (44)$$

describes the changes in $e(t)$ if $\theta(t) \neq 0$ initially. If the total torque is now specified as:

$$t = m_1 g l \cos \theta_d + m_1 K_p e(t) + m_1 K_v \dot{e}(t) + m_1 \ddot{\theta}_d \quad (45)$$

where the gains K_p and K_v need to be selected so that:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e(t) = 0 \quad (46)$$

It is shown in [2] that the new closed loop system with the torque law specified by (45) gives rise to a stable closed loop system if the choice is made:

$$\begin{aligned} K_p &> 2 g / l & (47a) \\ K_v &> 0 & (47b) \end{aligned}$$

What is interesting is the bound obtained via a majorizing function [2] as follows:

$$0 < \|e(t)\| < \|v(t)\| \quad (48)$$

and

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} v(t) = 0 \quad (49)$$

Thus $v(t)$ becomes the linear majorizing function. The eigenvalue of $v(t)$ closest to the origin is the dominant eigenvalue which describes the performance of the torque law in bounding $e(t)$. The proof of this procedure is carried out in detail in [2].

VI- Lyapunov Versus The Majorizing Function Method

The two advantages of the majorizing method over the Lyapunov method are as follows:

(1) The majorizing method can be used for any number of state variables greater than one. For second, third, or fourth order examples, it is easy to find $v(t)$. For the Lyapunov approach, any examples beyond one state variable are difficult to characterize. (2) Since the Lyapunov function depends on the square of the state variables, it is always conservative. The majorizing function approach, however, can be made less conservative.

A previous example (a reworked version of example 4) is now studied to compare the two methods.

Example 5: The system: $\dot{x}_1 = -(1/T) x_1$ (50)

$$V(x_1) = x_1^2 / 2 \quad (51)$$

has $W/V = dV/dt / V = -2/T$ (52)

Thus the time constant is twice the system's time constant. If $x_1(t)$ is a closed loop system operating under a closed loop control law, then:

$$v(t) = V(0) e^{-(2/T + \epsilon)t} \quad (53)$$

($\epsilon > 0$) would provide an exponential bound. Thus the majorizing approach is less conservative (more accurate). The last example considers the case of a second order state vector.

Example 6: For a reworked version of example (3), it

is observed: $\ddot{y} + \dot{y} + y = 0$ (54)

$$V = 1/2 \dot{y}^2 + 1/2 y^2 \quad (55)$$

$$W = dV/dt = -x_2^2 \quad (56)$$

Thus: $W/V = -x_2^2 / (1/2)(x_1^2 + x_2^2) = 2[-\dot{y} / (y + \dot{y}^2)]$ (57)

which is difficult to characterize except in phase space. Using the majorizing function approach, $v(t)$ can be selected so that:

$$0 < \|y(t)\| < \|v(t)\| \quad (58)$$

and with the first eigenvalue of $v(t)$ can be made approximately:

$$L_1 = -(1/2 + \epsilon) \quad (59)$$

For $\epsilon > 0$ to provide a less conservative bound.

VII- Some Integral Equation Approaches

For robotic systems, there are some powerful methods to study the modeling error or tracking error when integral equation inequalities are used. The Gromwell-Bellman inequality provides the fundamental approach:

Lemma 1: If $c > 0$, $u, v \geq 0$ for $t \geq 0$ and if:

$$u(t) = c + \int_0^t u(t_1) v(t_1) dt_1 \quad (60)$$

then: $u \leq c \exp \left[\int_0^t v(t_1) dt_1 \right]$ (61)

Thus an exponential bound on $u(t)$ can be found. This inequality gives rise to the Dini-Hukuhara Theorem for a column vector x :

Theorem 2: If all solutions of: $dx/dt = A x$ (62)

are bounded as $t \rightarrow \infty$, and if: $\int_0^{\infty} \|B\| dt < \infty$,

Then all solutions of:

$$dy/dt = (A + B(t)) y \quad (63)$$

are bounded as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

Applying the Gromwell-Bellman inequality, the following norm bound can be found:

$$\|y - x\| \leq \int_0^t \|e^{A(t-t_1)}\| \|B(t_1)\| \|y\| dt \quad (64)$$

If all eigenvalues of A have negative real parts, then it can be shown:

$$\|y\| \leq c_1 \exp \left(c \int_0^{\infty} \|B\| dt \right) \quad (65)$$

which is not quite as useful but leads up to the last theorem which is very useful [17]:

Theorem 3: If the eigenvalues of A have negative real parts, this yields: $\|x\| \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$

and $\|x(t)\| \leq c_2 e^{-a t}$ (66)

where a is the real part of the eigenvalue closest to the $j\omega$ axis. Then it follows that:

$$c_1 c_2 t^{-at} \quad (67)$$

Thus, if $c_1 c_2 < a$, then y is of exponential order with negative exponent ($c_1 c_2 - a$) and c_2 is defined in equation (66). Thus the modeling error is now bounded by a first order exponent. A final example will illustrate the applicability of this approach.

Example 7:

Assume the modeling error (or tracking error) of a one link robotic system satisfies: \ddot{e}

$$= (-8 + 2 \sin \sqrt{t} + (3/10) e^{-t}) e(t) \quad (68)$$

$$e(0) = 2 \quad (69)$$

Then the $x(t)$ equation is: $\dot{x} = -8x$ (70)

and $x(t) \leq (2)e^{-8t}$ (71)

Thus $a = -8$, $c_2 = 2$, and c_1 satisfies:
 $\|2 \sin \sqrt{t} + (3/10)e^{-t}\| = c_1 \leq 2.5$ (72)
 $(c_1 c_2 - a)t$

Thus: $e(t) \leq \frac{c_2 e^{-t}}{[(2.5)(3)-8]t} = \frac{2e^{-t}}{-1.5t}$ (73)

and $e(t) \leq \frac{2e^{-t}}{2e^{-0.5t}} = 2e^{-0.5t}$ (74)

which is now of exponential order and bounded. Thus the majorizing approach is more easily applied with the use of this theorem.

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Figure (1) - Constant V Curves

Figure (2) - V(t) and V-dot(t) versus t

Figure (3) - A One Link Robotic System